

SROC III

Third Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

**November, 2-3rd 2024,
Ethno Complex Vrdnicka kula, Vrdnik**

Physics Aspects of Total Body Irradiation

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13983188

Ivana Mišković¹

¹ *Institute of Oncology and Radiology of Serbia*

The strong arguments for radiotherapy as part of patient conditioning for bone marrow transplantation have led to the development of a series of techniques for a large body volume and total body irradiation (TBI). Due to the significant treated volume, the doses of several grays must be considered high, which necessitates high reliability and quality control in dosimetry. In this presentation, several physical aspects of TBI will be demonstrated, focusing on simple techniques and comfort for immobilized patient due to the certainty of dose delivery. The size of the treated volume does not allow the routine application of isocentric techniques, but imaging based dose modeling by reliable technical accessories of modern medical accelerators and volume dose calculation by confirmed planning systems, enables accurate whole body irradiation.

At an optimal 350 cm source-skin distance (SSD), the 40x40 field (at the isocenter) is diverged enough to irradiate the entire patient, who is translated 2.5m from the accelerator axis. This geometry affects the quality of the photon beam, the absorbed dose per monitor unit, the dose rate and the field penumbra. In addition, it enables the use of a simple radiation technique of two almost opposite fields. A certain degree of dose homogenization and dose control to the organs at risk, primarily the lungs, can still be achieved with the multi-leaf collimator system, in the case of lateral beams. Irradiating a side-lying patient requires additional lung protection by blocks. Scattered radiation on the spoiler, placed between the source and the patient, is absorbed by the skin and underskin domain, which compensates for the lack of dose in the build-up region of high-energy photons. The dose rate reduction is achieved by extending SSD and by decreasing the nominal accelerator dose rate. This fulfills the basic requirements of the TBI technique, with additional quality control provided by adapted EPID and the application of in-vivo dosimetry.

The initial measurements made during the implementation of the extended SSD TBI technique in the Institute of Oncology and Radiology of Serbia are shown in the speech. The technique is based on the TBI protocol used in Rigshospitalet (Denmark) and Royal Marsden Hospital (UK).

Keywords: total body irradiation, extended SSD, large field dosimetry

**SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress
2024**

Urednik
Olivera Ivanov

Izdavač
Institut za Onkologiju Vojvodine

Grafička priprema i štampa
NS digiprint, Novi Sad

Tiraž
200

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

CIP – Каталогизacija у публикацији
Библиотеке Матице српске, Нови Сад

616-006(048.3)

SERBIAN Radiation Oncology Congress (3 ; 2024 ; Vrdnik)

Abstract book / Third Serbian Radiation Oncology
Congress, SROC III, November, 2nd-3rd 2024, Ethno Complex
Vrdnicka Kula, Vrdnik ; [urednik Olivera Ivanov]. – Novi
Sad : Institut za onkologiju Vojvodine, 2024 (Novi Sad : NS
digiprint). – 60 str. ; 21 cm

Tiraž 200. – Str. 3: Introduction / Olivera Ivanov.

ISBN 978-86-82113-16-4

a) Онкологија – Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 155485193